

Extended Area Protection System (EAPS)

Program Overview

Brian J. Smith Roswell W. Nourse James L. Baumann George Sanders
RDECOM, AMRDEC
AMSRD-AMR-SG-RF
Redstone Arsenal, AL 35898
256-876-1330
Brian.Smith@rddec.redstone.army.mil

Abstract—The U.S. Army’s Aviation and Missile Research, Development, and Engineering Center (AMRDEC) is undertaking an Advanced Technology Objective (ATO) to provide active protection to U.S. forces against attack by Rockets, Artillery, and Mortars (RAM). Engaging and destroying RAM will reduce U.S. casualties, provide all freedom of movement, protect non-combatants, and safeguard military/civilian installations. Novel solutions are required to counter RAM cost effectively. This paper outlines activities being conducted under the EAPS ATO that are being investigated to protect U.S. interests against the RAM threat.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The primary defense against artillery and mortars since their introduction onto the battlefield has been avoidance and counter fire. Avoidance, usually in the form of digging and getting into a foxhole, denies freedom of movement during the attack, exposes troops to the first rounds fired, and does not protect material and installations. Major General (retired) Robert H. Scales, Jr.¹, historian and former commandant of the Army War College [1], summarizes the threat severity of contemporary limited conflicts in the following quote:

“...historically, in limited liability wars, ...the greatest killer of Americans on the battlefield is the mortar ...a platoon under mortar fire is relatively helpless.”

An effective active defense against RAM would decrease casualties, allow freedom of movement for combat troops, and protect vital facilities. However, there are many

challenges facing an attempt to engage and destroy RAM in flight. A key concern is that this is a low cost threat class; it would be difficult to sustain a fight for long where the tradeoff is using a million dollar interceptor to shoot down a minimal cost mortar or small rocket. Another key issue is threat density; it is possible to launch large numbers of RAM in an almost simultaneous attack. The small size of this threat class makes detection and successful engagement very stressing.

The U.S. Army’s AMRDEC has taken up the challenge of investigating and developing kinetic energy kill solutions to meet the RAM threat. A structured systems engineering approach is being taken on the EAPS ATO to insure an overall effective solution is obtained. Initial results indicate that merely applying traditional Air Defense (AD) technologies and system topologies could result in unaffordable material solutions. Hence, a key element of the EAPS program is the investigation of novel low cost solutions to engage and destroy the RAM threat.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The charge for the EAPS program is to develop and demonstrate enabling technologies for providing mobile, 360 degree hemispherical extended area protection from RAM threats. The program will demonstrate lethality, affordable bullet technologies, affordable missile technologies, and system architectures. Figure 1 is a notational depiction of how EAPS technology will integrate into the overall Extended Area Air Defense System (EAAPS) architecture. Current thought is that the EAPS components will operate inside of a 10 Km range. An initial effort in the program is addressing engagement/keep out range versus system cost/complexity as a function of engagement range.

A structured systems engineering approach is being taken to insure that a balanced, affordable system architecture is produced. A system requirements analysis is being undertaken to address engagement kinematics, interceptor velocity profiles, and system reaction time. Systems engineering management is being used to integrate the activities of the numerous program disciplines. This function benefits development phasing that controls the design process and provides baselines that coordinate design

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efforts. The system engineering process provides a structure for solving design problems and tracks requirements flow through the design effort. Life cycle integration that involves the customer is being used in the design process and ensures that the system developed is viable throughout its life.

The EAPS trade space for the various components of a missile system is depicted in Figure 2. Missile trades are being made between control systems, guidance technique, kill mechanism, and the launcher. Requirements will be generated for surveillance and fire control sensors and battle management, command, control and communications (BMC3I). The use and effect of external sensors on an EAPS system are also being considered during system development. Extensive use of modeling and simulation are being made to evaluate the various elements in the EAPS system.

3. THE THREAT

Examples of the types of threats under consideration by the EAPS program are shown in Figure 3. Mortars of 60-120mm, small rockets, and artillery up to 155mm are the primary targets with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and manned aircraft also under consideration as a residual capability. Characteristics of this threat class that make them difficult to counter include: low Radar Cross Sections (RCS), low trajectories, short flight times, thick cases, and high rates of fire. A detailed characterization of these threats is being undertaken as part of the EAPS program. The wide distribution and low cost of the RAM threat set requires the investigation of non-traditional approaches if a cost effect solution is to be developed.

4. SIMULATION APPROACH

Modeling and simulation are being used extensively on the EAPS program. Figure 4 shows the hierarchy of simulation tools in use. Engineering models are being developed to address the technical details of the program. Engineering models include simplified 5-Degree of Freedom (5-DOF) models as well as detailed 6-Degree of Freedom (6-DOF) simulations of the threat and EAPS interceptor and lethality prediction codes. These simulations feed a force-on-force model denoted as IDEEAS to determine the effectiveness of the proposed EAPS concepts in a combat setting. Finally, a campaign level simulation is used to address the overall effect of EAPS on the battlefield.

A novel approach has been taken for the development of the 6-DOF simulations. C++ Model Developer [2] (CMD) is an open-source C++ source code environment for building simulations of systems described by time-based differential equations. CMD is primarily for scientists and engineers who desire to use object-oriented features in developing complex numerical simulations of physical systems and mathematical functions. It is simple enough for students to use as a way of learning C++ and simulations modeling, but

at the same time is scalable from simple models to very complex simulations. It eliminates numerous code writing tasks by allowing the developer to focus on the physical aspects of the model and the type of numerical algorithms being implemented.

The heart of CMD is a powerful simulation kernel that represents significant technology advances in the application of object-oriented principles to simulation development and design. The kernel implements an object-oriented paradigm at all levels: the dynamic states are objects, the models themselves are objects, and the aggregate simulation is an object. Complex system model topologies are easily modeled using a unique "train-of-objects" paradigm. CMD has a powerful runtime dynamic asynchronous scheduling capability that allows seamless mixing of discrete and continuous dynamics models.

This Object Oriented architecture developed at the AMRDEC is being used to allow the development of the specific EAPS classes by subject matter experts and then integrated into the overall closed loop 6-DOF simulation. This approach will allow many interceptor concepts to be developed and evaluated rapidly with a maximum reuse of applicable code.

Laboratory, field, and live fire testing will be used to validate the models/simulations and key technologies.

5. PROGRAM PLAN

The Army's AMRDEC has been investigating the characteristics of the RAM threat and technologies to defeat this threat for several years. This preliminary work has helped to better define the problem and identify key technology barriers that must be overcome. A detailed program plan for overcoming the technology barriers has been developed and will be executed over the next 3 years as an Army ATO. Key technologies will be developed and demonstrated through laboratory testing, hardware-in-the-loop (HWIL), and captive flight tests. Current plans are to integrate all of the key technologies and perform missile flight tests in three years. Funding constraints, however, may limit the EAPS ATO to captive flight tests. An Advanced Technology Demonstration (ATD) could follow if results from the ATO are promising. Figure 5 shows a program time line. Affordability and combat effectiveness are key metrics that must be met if a fielded system is to be realized.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The U.S. Army is taking a major step in protecting its troops and facilities against the menacing RAM threat. The technical and cost difficulties in active defense against RAM require innovative approaches to all aspects of the threat. A structured systems engineering approach is being taken on the EAPS program to insure a balanced system architecture is obtained that will meet all requirements.

Advanced technologies will be integrated into the program as they develop to increase systems effectiveness and reduce interceptor and overall system cost.

REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

Brian Smith is an electronics engineer with the Applied Sensor, Guidance and Electronics Directorate, Missile Research, Development and Engineering Center, US RDECOM. He has worked in modeling and simulation of Air Defense Systems, Anti-Radiation Missiles, SAR/ISAR systems, data compression, and battlefield communications systems. He has conducted extensive research in localized computerized tomography for medical imaging and defense related areas. He holds a Ph.D. in Electrical and Computer Engineering from The University of Alabama in Huntsville and an MBA from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology where he was a Sloan Fellow.

George Sanders is an aerospace engineer with the Systems Simulation and Development Directorate, Missile Research, Development and Engineering Center, US RDECOM. He has worked in modeling and simulation of various Advanced Technology Objective (ATO) programs over the past 25 years. He currently serves as an experimental developer for Advanced Experimentation Functional Area where he is conducting research using genetic algorithms coupled with high-fidelity design codes

to synthesize and optimize the design of tactical missiles. He holds a BS in Aerospace Engineering from Auburn University.

James L. Baumann has a bachelor's degree in electrical engineering, master's degrees in automatic controls and system sciences, and a Ph.D. from the University of Alabama in Huntsville. He has 40 years experience in technology and system development to include: concept formulation, tradeoff analysis, specification development, selection among competing concepts, hardware prototyping, development testing, and transition of technology to full scale development. He has work for both large and small aerospace industries and for the Army Research, Development and Engineering Center (AMRDEC) in guided missile weapon systems. While at Redstone Arsenal, Dr. Baumann played key roles on teams that transitioned technology for precision laser guidance on the Apache helicopter and laser semi-active guidance for the 2.75 inch HYDRA 70 rocket. He is currently the AMRDEC Deputy Program Manager for the Extended Area Protection and Survivability (EAPS) Science and Technology Program to develop technology solutions to defeat multiple rocket, artillery, and mortar threats simultaneously

Figure 1. Notational Concept to Address Deficiencies in Future Force AD

EAPS Trade Space - Missile Concept

Figure 2. Trade Space Being Invested to Fulfill the EAPS Mission Requirements

Figure 3. The RAM Threat Spectrum Being Addressed by The EAPS Program

Figure 4. Simulation Toolset Being Used on the EAPS Program

Figure 5. EAPS Program Timeline